

DETERMINATION OF THE STABILITY AND SHELF LIFE OF ESCIN SUBSTANCE

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Introduction. The quality and stability of drugs are closely related concepts. Drug stability is influenced by several factors, including temperature, light, and humidity. Determining the shelf life of a drug is a crucial concern for specialists in the field of Pharmacy. It involves studying the processes during drug extraction, storage, transportation, and other factors to establish proper storage conditions and expiration dates. Standard stability tests are carried out to determine storage conditions and expiration dates in accordance with industry standards. However, conducting accelerated tests for certain thermolabile drug substances and types, especially herbal medicines, is challenging, leading to reliance on natural (continuous) tests as the primary method for determining stability. Positive results from accelerated tests can suggest that stability can be maintained despite short-term deviations under normal storage conditions. Real-time continuous testing plays a crucial role in determining and validating optimal shelf life after drug registration. These tests are conducted under conditions that closely simulate actual storage conditions when the drug is in circulation. Based on these considerations, the shelf life of Escin was determined only through natural testing.

Aim. The work aims to determine the stability and shelf life of Escin substance.

Methods. Over three years, a comprehensive study was carried out to investigate various aspects of a substance. The study focused on analyzing the appearance, solubility, identity, moisture content, presence of heavy metals, and triterpene glycoside (TTG) content of the substance. The identity of the Escin substance was determined using the thin layer chromatography (TLC) method. The extract was diluted and dripped onto a chromatographic plate (Merck, Germany) using a mixture of chloroform: anhydrous acetic acid: methanol: purified water (60:32:12: 8) as a solvent. The plate was left for 30 minutes to saturate, and a finish line was marked 12 cm away from the start line. Once the sample reached the finish line, the chromatography process was stopped, and the plate was removed. It was then treated with wet Iron (III) chloride and dried on a shelf at a temperature of 100 – 105 °C for 10 minutes. Subsequently, the plate was examined under a lamp at a wavelength of 366 nm. A noticeable purple stain was observed on both the Escin standard sample and the testing sample, indicating that they likely have the same R_f value. Furthermore, additional spots were also detected at various points within the testing solution. In addition, TTG was quantified using the high-performance liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry method, with a minimum requirement of 95.0% triterpene glycosides in the Escin substance compared to Escin.

Results. A comprehensive study spanning over three years was carried out to evaluate the stability and shelf life of the Escin substance. The investigation found that the quality indicators of the Escin substance, including its appearance, solubility, identity, moisture

content, presence of heavy metals, and TTG, consistently met the standards outlined in the pharmacopeia article for 2.5 years. However, at the end of the third year, it was noted that the moisture content of the Escin substance exceeded the specified limit of 2%, measuring at 2.9%. Consequently, the shelf life of the Escin substance was determined to be two years, as it showed no changes when stored naturally for 2.5 years.

Conclusion. The quality indicators of Escin substance, including its physical and chemical properties, such as its appearance, solubility, and identity, as well as its moisture content, absence of heavy metals, and TTG, have all been thoroughly assessed. The results demonstrate that the substance fully complies with the stringent requirements outlined in the pharmacopeia article. Furthermore, an extensive stability study revealed that when Escin substance was stored under natural conditions for 2.5 years, there were no discernible changes in its properties. Consequently, based on this extensive study, it has been determined that the shelf life of the Escin substance is two years.